

Design and Construction of a Centrifugal Pump Test Bed

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Abstract:- This project work details the design, manufacture, and testing of a centrifugal pump. The centrifugal pump is driven by an electric motor, which is also linked to a tachometer, a variable frequency drive and a wattmeter, which measure the speed of the motor shafts and the electrical power of the pump, respectively. The driven centrifugal pump pulls fluid (water) from a sump reservoir and transfers it to a tank through a flow control valve. We were able to conduct the experiments required to completely describe a centrifugal pump using the demonstration unit. The correlations between the different parameters, such as head (H), efficiency (η), rotational speed (ω), and input power (Pi), and the flow rate (Q), were also generated in tabular and graphical form. The experimental findings acquired at the conclusion of this study demonstrate that the tested pump can achieve a head (H_{max}) of 35m, a volumetric discharge (Q_{max}) of 35l/min, and a speed of 2850 rpm with an input power of 0.5HP. The pump's performance was reported to be very smooth, with minimal vibration and noise levels on both the pump and the motor, ensuring the pump's reliability in service.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fluid mechanics students have long respected the concept of centrifugal pumps and their characteristics in terms of understanding the many equations that predict their performance under various operating conditions. Centrifugal pumps have a wide range of commercial and industrial uses, including the oil and gas business, steam power plants, buildings, agriculture and irrigation, the food industry, and the paper and pulp industry (Sharma and Rai, 2013). Added to the need for fluid mechanics students to not only understand the equations that predict the performance of these pumps under various operating conditions through calculations, but also provide them with hands-on experience through specialized training in their fluid mechanics laboratory, giving them a competitive advantage in the industry. Hence, a need for the design and construction of a centrifugal pump test bed for student use at the fluid mechanics laboratory.

The stated scope of this work is to design, build, and experimentally investigate centrifugal pump performance or to test an educational demonstration or instructional unit to allow undergraduate students to evaluate the behavior of centrifugal pumps in a variety of operating conditions, as inspired by the above literature. The unit will be used to supplement a fluid mechanics engineering science course by giving mechanical engineering students hands-on experience with pump performance characterization. Pump efficiency will also be measured directly. All experimental pump performance data should be compared to manufacturer's

pump performance data as well as theoretical projections. Choate and Lenoir (Choate and Lenoir, 2008).

As previously stated, these pumps are used to transport liquids from one location to another. As a result, they are an effective tool for teaching students the relationships between pressure or head, volumetric flow rate, shaft rotational speeds, and input and output powers, effectively bridging the gap between theory and practice. The test bed is designed to give students an instructional tool that they may use to conduct various experiments to demonstrate the physical and functional links between these characteristics.

The test bed is capable of measuring pressures (pressures at the pump inlet or suction and outlet or discharge sides of the pump), volume flow rates, pump shaft rotational speeds, and shaft torques or forces with moment arms, based on the background outlined. The water flow rate is controlled by manually operated valves at the pump inlets and outputs, which aid the student experimenter in intuitively arranging the flow for the suggested designed centrifugal pump configuration.

These pumps allowed fluid to be transported between two locations by harnessing power from another source (steam turbines and electric motors). Centrifugal pumps are a form of dynamic pressure pump that generates head and flow by raising the liquid's velocity with the help of a rotating vane impeller and diffuser. The performance of such pumps is influenced by factors such as specific speed, blade orientation, casing insulation, impeller diameter, number and pitch of blades, internal surface finish, liquid viscosity, and so on (Sharma and Rai, 2013). The rotating element, which consists of an impeller and a shaft, and the stationary element, which consists of a casing, casing cover, and bearings, are the major components of this type of pump (Karrassik, 2011). Other components, however, are required to complete a centrifugal pump assembly.

The centrifugal force of the impeller blade converts mechanical energy into hydraulic energy of the handling fluid, allowing it to be transported to a desired location or height. Newton's second law governs their operation. Due to the mechanical energy on the driven impeller, the fluid at the internal radius flows to the outer radius, gaining the centrifugal head and causing suction at the pump inlet known as the eye. The fluid that is pumped by this sort of pump receives useful energy through velocity variations when the fluid goes through the impeller of the pumps. Mechanical energy, such as an electrical motor on the drive shaft driven by a prime mover or a small engine, is used to operate this pump. The hydraulic energy of the fluid being elevated or conveyed is the output energy. The liquid is driven into a series of revolving vanes by atmospheric or other pressure in a centrifugal pump. These rotating vanes are contained within

a housing or casing and are used to transmit energy to a fluid via centrifugal force (Khin, Mya, and Khin, 2008).

Long service life, non-toxic effects, local availability, cheap cost, easy handling during building and fabrication, lightness of weight for easy handling during usage, and supplying caster wheels for easy movability were all essential considerations in the design of this centrifugal pump test bed. The frame is built of mild steel that is welded in a rectangular shape in both vertical and horizontal directions to increase rigidity. The system's components are held in place by the supports. With a vertical elevation of 1117.6mm, the frame is approximately 1270mm long and 457.2mm wide. The centrifugal pump was not designed because it was beyond the scope of this project. However, an arbitrary centrifugal pump was obtained from the market, with suction and exit pipe diameters matching the size of the pipe ran on the bed, in order to characterize it (the pump) using the test bed. The chosen 0.5H pump has a 35m total head inscription on its nameplate and runs at a maximum speed of 2850rpm. Two fluid (water) reservoirs make up the test rig. The larger reservoir (469.9mm in length, 457.2mm in width, and 558.8mm in height) is supported by a steel support base (495.3mm by 457.2mm with a thickness of 1.5mm). The smaller reservoir is supported by a 495.3mm by 457.2mm steel support base with 1.5mm thickness that is 635mm high from the big reservoir and is perforated at the bottom side of the reservoir to allow pipe to go through to the bigger reservoir from the smaller one.

Two pressure gauges were chosen, one for the suction side and the other for the discharge side of the pump. The discharge side readings had a range of 0-100 psi, whereas the suction side gauges had a range of -30 in-Hg to 15 psi. The electrical power of the pump was measured using a Wattmeter, and the rotational speed of the electric motor, which corresponds to the pump speed, was measured with a tachometer. The outboard end of an electric motor is usually left exposed to allow the tachometer spindle to rest against a recess in the motor shaft. The mass flow rate of the fluid (water) was measured using a flow meter with an inner diameter of 25.4mm, and the water flow rate before and after the pump was controlled using manually operated valves at the pump inlets and outputs.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Consider the energy transfer of a pump by applying the steady state form of the energy equation as follows in order to completely comprehend the function of the centrifugal pump.

$$Q + W = m_{\text{outlet}} \left[h + \frac{v^2}{2} + gz \right]_{\text{outlet}} - m_{\text{inlet}} \left[h + \frac{v^2}{2} + gz \right]_{\text{inlet}} \quad (1)$$

Defining the enthalpy, h , in Equation (1), therefore, h ;

$$h = u + Pv = u + \frac{P}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

And by conservation of mass of the centrifugal pump's axial input and tangential output:

$$m_{\text{outlet}} = m_{\text{inlet}} \quad (3)$$

This implies that on a per unit mass basis, $m = m_{\text{outlet}} = m_{\text{inlet}}$:

$$q + w_s = \left[u + \frac{P}{\rho} + \frac{v^2}{2} + gz \right]_{\text{outlet}} - \left[u + \frac{P}{\rho} + \frac{v^2}{2} + gz \right]_{\text{inlet}} \quad (4)$$

because the flow is incompressible, equation (3) shows that the inlet and outlet velocities are equal if the inlet and outlet areas are roughly similar. Furthermore, there is a minor change in potential energy across the pump, resulting in;

$$\left(\frac{P}{\rho g} \right)_{\text{outlet}} - \left(\frac{P}{\rho g} \right)_{\text{inlet}} = \frac{w}{g} - \frac{U_2 - U_1 - q}{g} \quad (5)$$

The last group of terms represents frictional losses and is grouped into a frictional head loss term, h_f . similarly, expressing the shaft work input into the pump as a shaft work head term, h_s , yields:

$$H = \frac{1}{\rho g} (P_{\text{outlet}} - P_{\text{inlet}}) = h_s - h_f \quad (6)$$

HERE, H is the "net" or "pump" head and is the primary output parameter for a pump. Note also that this is the difference between the shaft work and the frictional head ($h_s - h_f$).

The energy that is been delivered to the fluid is as a result of the difference between the input energy and the energy lost to friction, both mechanical and viscous, and losses due to pump leakage. The power delivered to the fluid is by tradition termed the "water horsepower" or whp, and therefore, represented as:

$$\text{whp} = \rho g V H \quad (7)$$

Where V , g , and H are the volumetric flow rate of the fluid, the density of water, acceleration due to gravity and the head of the pump respectively.

In contrast, the power required to drive the pump is termed the "brake horsepower" or bhp:

$$\text{bhp} = \omega T \quad (8)$$

Where T is the measured shaft torque and ω is the shaft rotational speed in radians per second. The overall efficiency of the pump is defined as the ratio between the power delivered to the fluid (power required to move the fluid) and the pump input power.

Recall, whp is the "water horsepower" while bhp is the "brake horsepower, therefore, the efficiency of the pump is;

$$\eta_{\text{pump}} = \frac{\text{whp}}{\text{bhp}} = \frac{\rho g V H}{\omega T} \quad (9)$$

This overall efficiency is a function of both mechanical and fluid losses.

The viscous frictional effects and mechanical frictional effects in the bearings, packing and other contact points in the pump are the contributing factors to the overall efficiency of the pump.

The most suitable mechanical engineering software that can be used to systematically analysis and easily evaluate the working efficiency of the centrifugal pump rest bed is the solid works. The testing points are at the inlet to the pump and at its exit. Also we test for the variation of head, input power and pump performance i.e. the pump efficiency with discharge.

The correlation used to calculate total head, discharge, efficiency, specific speed and power has been given by the expressions.

$$\text{Input power of motor to the shaft} = (\text{Number of revolution} \times 3600) \div (\text{time} \times Z \times W) \quad (10)$$

Input power to the pump = (input power of motor to the shaft) \times (transmission efficiency)

$$Q = \frac{(W \times L \times h)}{t} \quad (11)$$

Where h is the height of water in collecting tank and W and L are width and length of the collecting tank respectively (all in m). Discharge is denoted by Q (m³/s).

The total head (H) estimated by the relation

$$H = H_s + H_d \quad (12)$$

Where H_s and H_d used for suction Head and discharge Head in (m) respectively.

$$P_o = \rho \cdot g \cdot Q \cdot H \quad (13)$$

Where ρ , g and P_o represents the density of water, acceleration due to gravity and output power (P_o) respectively.

The efficiency estimated through the relation given:

$$\text{Efficiency } (\eta) = (\text{Hydraulic power output}) \div (\text{Input power}) \quad (14)$$

$$\eta_{\text{pump}} = \frac{whp}{bhp} = \frac{\rho g V H}{\omega T} \quad (15)$$

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

• **Materials (Equipment):** After doing research into viable possibilities for the system's various equipment, performing technical calculations, and properly justifying all aspects of the centrifugal pump test bed. The equipment was chosen based on requirement and market availability. The major equipment that will be integrated into the final system includes: the bench frame on which the whole assembly is

mounted, the reservoir on a platform, valves fitted on inlet and delivery pipes, the piping system, flow meter, stop watch, pressure gauge, the pump, electric motor, caster wheels, strainers, thermometer, fittings and flexible hose, variable frequency drives (Advanced inverter). Each piece of equipment was chosen based on its use, cost effectiveness, and market availability. Each of these elements is briefly discussed in the following sections:

- **The Bench Frame:** Stress and deflection analysis was used to choose and design the bench frame material. We were able to relate the analysis results to material properties so that we can choose the best material from the material group. The material chosen have good ductility, strength, corrosion-resistant, and was locally sorted (cheap). Mild steel have been chosen as the preferred material for this design.
- **The Reservoir:** For the water reservoir, we chose a polyethylene rectangular tank. It came with a steel platform that was designed to support the maximum amount of water.
- **The Valves:** The system consists of a ball valve for the input (suction valve) and a ball valve for the output (discharge valve).
- **The Piping Network:** PVC tubing and fittings were used to construct the plumbing network, which includes the necessary elbows, tees, reducers, diameter change adapters, and valves.
- **Water Flow Meter and Stop Watch:** The volume of water leaving the pump from the discharge line is measured using water flow meters. In order to calculate the flow rate, a stopwatch is also required.
- **Pressure Gauges:** There are two different gauges that were chosen, one for the suction side and the other for the discharge side of the pump. The discharge side gauge should have a standard precision, whereas the suction side gauge should have a higher precision.
- **The Pump:** A centrifugal pump connected to an electric motor was selected. Pump motor specification includes 1-hp, 220-230 volts, single to three phase conversion, and had an advance inverter with variable frequency controllers that could be programmed for varied speeds and constant or varying torque.
- **Caster Wheels:** Heavy-duty caster wheels were chosen to allow for easy movement of the system from one location to another while also uniformly carrying the weight of the complete system without distortion.
- **Strainers:** At the end of the suction line, which is subsequently connected to the reservoirs, strainers are connected. This allows for particle separation while also protecting downstream equipment (pump, instrumentation) from renegade garbage.

IV. MATERIAL SELECTION AND SPECIFICATION

Material selection is an important part of the design process for any physical object. The basic purpose of material selection in product design is to minimize cost while maximizing product performance in order to fulfill the

product goal. Material selection entails finding the best match between the material's property-profile in its kingdom and the design's requirements (Ashby, 2005).

S/N	Part	Description of use	Quantity
1	Mild steel	It's what the bench frame is made of	1
2	Carbon steel	It's for mounting the pump and motor bed.	1
3	Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) Pipes	It is used for the piping system	
4	Fibre glass rectangular tank	It is used for m the reservoir	1
5	Pressure gauges	It is used to take the pressure readings at the inlet and outlet lines	2
6	Ball valves	It is used to control flow	3
7	Water flow meter	It is used to calculate the volume flow rate.	1

Table 1: List of Materials Selection

- **Mild Steel:** One of the most widely utilized construction materials is mild steel. Because of its low carbon concentration, it is referred to as mild steel. Mild steel has a maximum carbon content of 40 points (i.e. 0.4 percent carbon). Other alloying elements, besides carbon, are used to give steel its desirable mechanical characteristics, such as corrosion resistance and strength. Mild steel is extremely strong due to its low carbon content. Even when cold, it is extremely flexible. This indicates that the material has a high tensile and impart strength (Scott et al., 2018). Mild steel was chosen for the bench structure because of its weldability, machinability, and the fact that it is constructed of widely available natural resources.
- **Dimensions of the bench frame:** The bench frame, which is made completely of a 2mm hollow square mild steel of dimension 50mm × 50mm × 2mm. The bench frame has the following dimensions: length = 1270mm, height = 1117.6mm, width = 457.2mm, and overall dimension = 1270mm × 1117.6mm × 457.2mm
Therefore, the weight of the hollow square mild steel section, $W = \text{volume} \times \text{density}$
Recall: The density of mild steel is 7850 kg/m.
Volume = Area × Length
(16)
- **Carbon Steel:** Carbon steel is a type of steel that consists of an iron and carbon alloy. In comparison to stainless steel, it has a larger carbon content, a lower melting point, and is more durable. The tensile strength and hardness of carbon steel are both high. The baseplate is made of carbon steel to provide flat, coplanar surfaces on which to install the pump, driver, and reservoir. The baseplate is either welded to the base frame or secured by foundation bolts, providing for vibration-free pump performance and the ability to support the weight of the pump and reservoir without distortion (Towsley, 2009).
- **Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) Pipes:** PVC is a typical building material that is both robust and light. Plasticizers are used to make it softer and more flexible. PVC (unplasticized polyvinyl chloride) or hard PVC is what it's called when no plasticizers are applied. PVC was chosen

for the pipe network because of its hardness, density (when compared to other polymers, it has a specific gravity of about 1.4), and tensile strength. It is also widely accessible and inexpensive. A concentric reducer is utilized at the pump's suction line, whereas an eccentric reducer is used at the discharge line.

- **Fiber Glass Rectangular Tank:** Fiber Glass was designed and built into a rectangular tank that will be used as the reservoir for this test. The tank can hold 90 liters of water at a time.
- **Pressure Gauge:** To measure the pressures at the discharge and suction lines, two pressure gauges are utilized and linked at the suction and discharge lines.
- **Ball valve:** A ball valve is a type of quarter-turn valve that controls flow through a hollow, perforated, and rotating ball. It opens when the ball's hole is parallel to the flow and closes when the valve handle is rotated 90 degrees. Two ball valves were selected and attached to the discharge and suction lines, respectively. Ball valves often allow for partial opening and shutting, making them ideal for this application.

V. DESIGN CONSIDERATION

Design of Frame

The bench frame is made of mild steel material which consists of a hollow square dimensions 25.4mm × 25.4mm × 25.4mm. This material was chosen because of its light nature, tensile and impart strength and its ability to resist bending. It consists of two platforms; the first is the lower platform on which the reservoir is mounted and the second upper platform on which the electric motor and centrifugal pump is mounted. Various dimensions of the bed and platform are: length of the bed = 1270mm, height of the bed = 1117.6mm, width of the bed = 457.2mm.
Total dimensions of the bed = length × height × breath
(17)

Total dimensions of the bed = 1270mm × 1117.6mm × 45

Model name: UCHE PROJECT
 Current Configuration: Default<As Machined>

Beam Bodies:

Document Name and Reference	Formulation	Properties	Document Path/Date Modified
SolidBody 1(Trim/Extend21[2]) 	Beam – Uniform C/S	Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m ² Length:431.8mm Volume:0.000581968m ³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m ³ Mass:4.53935kg Weight:44.4856N	C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDPRT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021
SolidBody 3(Trim/Extend5[2]) 	Beam – Uniform C/S	Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m ² Length:1,270mm Volume:0.00171169m ³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m ³ Mass:13.3512kg Weight:130.841N	C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDPRT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021
SolidBody 4(Trim/Extend14[2]) 	Beam – Uniform C/S	Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m ² Length:596.9mm Volume:0.000804492m ³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m ³ Mass:6.27504kg Weight:61.4954N	C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDPRT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021
SolidBody 5(Trim/Extend16[2]) 	Beam – Uniform C/S	Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m ² Length:1,117.6mm Volume:0.00150628m ³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m ³ Mass:11.749kg Weight:115.14N	C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDPRT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021
SolidBody 6(Trim/Extend7[2]) 	Beam – Uniform C/S	Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m ² Length:457.2mm Volume:0.000616215m ³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m ³ Mass:4.80648kg Weight:47.1035N	C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDPRT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021

<p>SolidBody 7(Trim/Extend12[2])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:596.9mm Volume:0.000804502m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:6.27511kg Weight:61.4961N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 8(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[4])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/angle iron Section Area: 0.000179762m² Length:455.023mm Volume:8.17947e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.637998kg Weight:6.25238N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 9(Trim/Extend10[1])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:457.2mm Volume:0.000616215m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:4.80648kg Weight:47.1035N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 10(Trim/Extend14[1])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:520.7mm Volume:0.000701799m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:5.47404kg Weight:53.6456N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 12(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[2])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/angle iron Section Area: 0.000179762m² Length:529.265mm Volume:9.51404e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.742095kg Weight:7.27253N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 13(Trim/Extend22[1])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:1,155.7mm Volume:0.00155765m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:12.1497kg Weight:119.067N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>

<p>SolidBody 14(Trim/Extend16[1])</p>	Beam – Uniform C/S	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:1,270mm Volume:0.00171169m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:13.3512kg Weight:130.841N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 15(Rectangular tube - configured 3 X 2 X 0.25(1)[15])</p>	Beam – Uniform C/S	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:381mm Volume:0.0005135m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:4.0053kg Weight:39.252N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 16(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[4])</p>	Beam – Uniform C/S	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/angle iron Section Area: 0.000179762m² Length:529.265mm Volume:9.51404e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.742095kg Weight:7.27253N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 18(Square tube - configured 20 X 20 X 2(1)[1])</p>	Beam – Uniform C/S	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/square tube Section Area: 0.000133699m² Length:457.2mm Volume:6.11272e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.476792kg Weight:4.67257N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 19(Trim/Extend18[1])</p>	Beam – Uniform C/S	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:1,155.7mm Volume:0.00155765m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:12.1497kg Weight:119.067N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 20(Trim/Extend20[1])</p>	Beam – Uniform C/S	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:1,155.7mm Volume:0.00155765m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:12.1497kg Weight:119.067N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>

<p>SolidBody 21(Square tube - configured 20 X 20 X 2(1)[2])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/square tube Section Area: 0.000133699m² Length:457.2mm Volume:6.11272e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.476792kg Weight:4.67257N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 22(Trim/Extend13[2])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:457.2mm Volume:0.000616208m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:4.80642kg Weight:47.1029N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 23(Trim/Extend11[2])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:520.7mm Volume:0.000701791m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:5.47397kg Weight:53.6449N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 24(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[3])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/angle iron Section Area: 0.000179762m² Length:533.26mm Volume:9.58584e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.747696kg Weight:7.32742N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 25(Rectangular tube - configured 3 X 2 X 0.25(1)[17])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:381mm Volume:0.0005135m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:4.0053kg Weight:39.252N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 26(Square tube - configured 20 X 20 X 2(1)[3])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/square tube Section Area: 0.000133699m² Length:457.2mm Volume:6.11272e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.476792kg Weight:4.67257N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>

<p>SolidBody 27(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[1])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/angle iron Section Area: 0.000179762m² Length:533.26mm Volume:9.58584e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.747696kg Weight:7.32742N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 28(Trim/Extend20[2])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:419.1mm Volume:0.000564851m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:4.40584kg Weight:43.1772N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 29(Trim/Extend18[2])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:1,244.6mm Volume:0.00167744m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:13.084kg Weight:128.223N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 30(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[3])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/angle iron Section Area: 0.000179762m² Length:455.023mm Volume:8.17947e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.637998kg Weight:6.25238N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 31(Trim/Extend22[2])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/ansi inch/rectangular tube Section Area: 0.00134777m² Length:1,244.6mm Volume:0.00167745m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:13.0841kg Weight:128.224N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
<p>SolidBody 32(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[1])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/angle iron Section Area: 0.000179762m² Length:455.023mm Volume:8.17947e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.637998kg Weight:6.25238N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDP RT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>

<p>SolidBody 33(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[2])</p>	<p>Beam – Uniform C/S</p>	<p>Section Standard-weldment profiles/iso/angle iron Section Area: 0.000179762m² Length:455.023mm Volume:8.17947e-05m³ Mass Density:7,800kg/m³ Mass:0.637998kg Weight:6.25238N</p>	<p>C:\Users\hausb\Desktop\New folder\UCHE PROJECT.SLDPRT Dec 23 08:10:27 2021</p>
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Table 2: Finite Element Analysis (FEA) for the Bed Frame (Model Information)

7.2mm

(18)

Beam Name	Joints	Axial(N)	Shear1(N)	Shear2(N)	Moment1(N.m)	Moment2(N.m)	Torque(N.m)
Beam-1(Trim/Extend21[2])	1	162.317	-161.724	-1.28373	0.529748	-18.3237	-1.39716
	2	-132.025	-331.774	-10.3292	-0.864748	24.7936	-2.14763
Beam-2(Trim/Extend5[2])	1	96.7581	491.202	14.1514	-6.24192	68.816	1.79105
	2	-92.0843	482.863	-6.51065	-4.42081	-63.2292	4.26825
	3	-93.2924	275.096	-6.54821	-2.93887	38.1968	3.06621
	4	-94.9827	49.1844	-7.82688	-1.36171	85.1525	0.666366
	5	-96.7567	-176.241	-14.1514	0.581335	64.6726	-1.79107
Beam-3(Trim/Extend14[2])	1	-1,954.63	-94.2776	23.1294	15.6003	34.9394	0.832173
	2	1,954.63	94.2776	-23.1294	-2.08203	20.1622	-0.832173
Beam-4(Trim/Extend16[2])	1	2,505.93	-46.7134	91.6038	-22.9898	-9.22093	-0.72499
	2	-455.064	128.384	2.634	9.05861	-25.9076	-3.81115
	3	-2,505.93	46.7108	-91.6038	-35.1786	-20.4413	0.724996
Beam-5(Trim/Extend7[2])	1	-139.357	-503.906	-40.9353	-9.30792	30.8456	21.1113
	2	139.357	-496.094	40.9353	-9.40771	-29.0596	-21.1113
Beam-6(Trim/Extend12[2])	1	1,974.08	-55.6549	-28.2609	-0.100456	-8.61061	-0.451188
	2	-1,974.08	55.6529	28.2609	16.6179	-23.917	0.45118
Beam-7(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[4])	1	-55.5239	57.9831	2.77567	0.0602829	0.694245	0.0043753
	2	80.6722	76.7685	-3.51922	-0.380681	-1.37987	-0.00479154
	3	80.6722	76.7685	-3.51922	-0.380681	-1.37987	-0.00479154
Beam-8(Trim/Extend10[1])	1	-20.8074	-490.331	-24.9532	-5.68332	16.1708	-14.4169
	2	20.8074	-509.669	24.9532	-5.72527	-20.5914	14.4169
Beam-9(Trim/Extend14[1])	1	491.558	797.497	72.968	5.4457	-19.8866	2.16575
	2	-407.306	807.896	89.7625	-7.1796	26.9029	-0.656658
Beam-10(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[2])	1	-74.1544	76.6596	4.89387	-0.00915648	-1.43548	-0.0043654
	2	-3.54613	63.9985	2.37607	0.0884885	1.14971	-0.00877809
Beam-11(Trim/Extend22[1])	1	0.609344	-0.0716898	-0.0775552	-0.00785465	0.00731674	-0.000105642
	2	-995.108	-153.508	-137.692	-47.7047	29.0545	-3.06601
	3	-0.609344	0.0716898	0.0775552	0.0117742	-0.0109398	0.000105642
	4	-3,015.53	-33.2135	-94.8453	-35.6485	14.8405	0.186647
Beam-12(Trim/Extend16[1])	1	38.3013	-41.0301	10.9721	-5.59623	-30.17	-3.15196
	2	1.26674	264.747	-6.93822	-4.47022	-3.3529	-0.933755
	3	2.47483	47.3172	-6.90106	-2.87316	39.6743	-1.94056

Beam Name	Joints	Axial(N)	Shear1(N)	Shear2(N)	Moment1(N.m)	Moment2(N.m)	Torque(N.m)
	4	4.16516	-199.212	-5.62157	-1.18835	18.5764	-4.25397
	5	-38.3021	355.99	-10.975	1.20722	-49.2342	3.15195
Beam-13(Rectangular tube - configured 3 X 2 X 0.25(1)[15])	1	-97.2521	-266.387	6.88073	0.454116	17.8562	1.10513
	2	104.693	-281.249	3.15774	-0.3487	-18.2557	1.37909
Beam-14(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[4])	1	-3.65557	65.8996	-7.7172	0.584323	1.34084	-0.00407561
	2	-44.0093	80.8013	-16.7008	-0.854206	-1.79645	0.0020938
Beam-15(Square tube - configured 20 X 20 X 2(1)[1])	1	0.037546	-1.20799	4.83125	-1.20205	-0.275913	0.246345
	2	-0.0375763	1.20799	-4.83125	-1.0068	-0.27638	-0.246345
Beam-16(Trim/Extend18[1])	1	-774.416	27.746	23.6864	17.7698	-19.6577	-1.25505
	2	774.416	-27.746	-23.6864	8.70214	-11.3512	1.25505
Beam-17(Trim/Extend20[1])	1	-973.194	-14.2967	67.1311	48.8122	11.9026	-1.26251
	2	973.194	14.2967	-67.1311	26.2135	4.07547	1.26251
Beam-18(Square tube - configured 20 X 20 X 2(1)[2])	1	1.27864	-1.69011	10.309	-2.39985	-0.38725	0.139982
	2	-1.2787	1.69011	-10.309	-2.31343	-0.385468	-0.139982
Beam-19(Trim/Extend13[2])	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	2	-249.207	-824.854	89.9316	-5.53954	-34.2108	-0.490359
Beam-20(Trim/Extend11[2])	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	2	393.028	752.775	-36.8869	-2.83424	-20.857	-3.27107
Beam-21(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[3])	1	-124.303	67.3984	-6.81214	0.457602	1.33297	-0.00966696
	2	106.772	57.5606	-0.227124	-0.218747	-0.949554	6.88073e-05
	3	-124.303	67.3984	-6.81214	0.457602	1.33297	-0.00966696
Beam-22(Rectangular tube - configured 3 X 2 X 0.25(1)[17])	1	-401.731	-802.63	-95.1677	4.20569	-28.3212	2.32356
	2	458.049	-747.369	-55.5815	-2.17296	25.4388	-0.428802
Beam-23(Square tube - configured 20 X 20 X 2(1)[3])	1	6.32453	-1.77411	10.7949	-2.45744	-0.404962	-0.197873
	2	-6.32459	1.77411	-10.7949	-2.47798	-0.40616	0.197873
Beam-24(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[1])	1	-86.8774	59.9097	-0.874171	0.198861	0.967914	-4.74504e-05
	2	81.2163	59.9514	-0.759041	-0.211149	-0.967921	0.000258004
Beam-25(Trim/Extend20[2])	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beam-26(Trim/Extend18[2])	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
	3	-0.00166562	-0.000170213	-4.25232e-06	-9.65429e-07	3.86399e-05	-1.43756e-07
Beam-27(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[3])	1	-31.9751	55.5977	2.00599	0.0557796	0.718132	-0.0161505
	2	21.5165	66.6675	4.01536	-0.125364	-1.09339	-0.0115089

Beam Name	Joints	Axial(N)	Shear1(N)	Shear2(N)	Moment1(N.m)	Moment2(N.m)	Torque(N.m)
Beam-28(Trim/Extend22[2])	1	232.037	325.164	12.0624	-0.800133	27.5228	-1.47922
	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
	3	-0.00125351	-0.00012919	-3.33109e-06	-7.57612e-07	2.93636e-05	-1.1274e-07
Beam-29(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[1])	1	-5.61572	96.7018	-23.1329	-0.912381	-1.9874	0.00926447
	2	1.85065	96.3714	-24.0195	0.93329	1.98046	0.00773203
Beam-30(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[2])	1	46.2369	58.9081	0.697447	-0.0874389	-0.670669	0.0037764
	2	-36.5969	57.7096	0.585193	0.0583377	0.597631	0.000847953

Table 3: Beams (Beam Forces)

Beam Name	Joints	Axial(N/m^2)	Bending Dir1(N/m^2)	Bending Dir2(N/m^2)	Torsional (N/m^2)	Upper bound axial and bending(N/m^2)
Beam-1(Trim/Extend21[2])	1	-120,434	-28,071.3	-759,641	-51,672.1	908,146
	2	-97,957.9	-45,822.8	-1.02786e+06	-79,427.5	1.17164e+06
Beam-2(Trim/Extend5[2])	1	-71,791.3	330,758	2.85288e+06	66,239.9	3.25543e+06
	2	-68,323.5	-234,258	2.62127e+06	157,856	2.92385e+06
	3	-69,219.8	-155,730	-1.58351e+06	113,400	1.80846e+06
	4	-70,474	-72,156.8	-3.53014e+06	24,644.7	3.67277e+06
	5	-71,790.2	30,804.8	-2.68111e+06	-66,240.5	2.78371e+06
Beam-3(Trim/Extend14[2])	1	-1.45027e+06	826,655	-1.44847e+06	30,776.7	3.72539e+06
	2	-1.45027e+06	110,326	835,858	-30,776.7	2.39645e+06
Beam-4(Trim/Extend16[2])	1	-1.85932e+06	1.21823e+06	-382,269	-26,812.7	3.45981e+06
	2	-337,642	480,014	1.07404e+06	-140,950	1.8917e+06
	3	-1.85932e+06	-1.8641e+06	847,427	26,812.9	4.57085e+06
Beam-5(Trim/Extend7[2])	1	-103,398	-493,225	-1.27875e+06	780,770	1.87538e+06
	2	-103,398	498,512	-1.20471e+06	-780,770	1.80662e+06
Beam-6(Trim/Extend12[2])	1	-1.4647e+06	5,323.12	-356,967	-16,686.5	1.82699e+06
	2	-1.4647e+06	880,577	991,517	16,686.2	3.3368e+06
Beam-7(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[4])	1	308,875	979,947	1.87365e+06	98,316.6	3.16247e+06
	2	448,773	1.20613e+06	3.29142e+06	-107,670	4.94632e+06
	3	448,773	1.20613e+06	3.29142e+06	-107,670	4.94632e+06
Beam-8(Trim/Extend10[1])	1	-15,438.4	-301,158	-670,388	-533,189	986,984
	2	-15,438.4	303,381	-853,653	533,189	1.17247e+06
Beam-9(Trim/Extend14[1])	1	364,720	288,566	824,434	80,097.5	1.47772e+06
	2	302,207	380,445	1.1153e+06	-24,285.7	1.79796e+06
Beam-10(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[2])	1	-412,515	2.35453e+06	4.06564e+06	-98,094.1	6.83269e+06
	2	19,726.8	1.6551e+06	3.12169e+06	-197,251	4.79652e+06
Beam-11(Trim/Extend22[1])	1	-452.112	416.216	303.328	-3.90704	1,171.66
	2	-738,337	-2.52786e+06	-1.2045e+06	-113,393	4.4707e+06
	3	-452.112	623.91	453.529	3.90704	1,529.55
	4	-2.23743e+06	-1.88901e+06	-615,238	6,902.9	4.74167e+06
Beam-12(Trim/Extend16[1])	1	-28,418.2	296,543	-1.25075e+06	-116,571	1.57571e+06
	2	939.876	-236,876	139,000	-34,533.6	376,816
	3	1,836.24	-152,248	-1.64476e+06	-71,769	1.79885e+06
	4	3,090.41	-62,970.6	-770,114	-157,327	836,176
	5	-28,418.8	63,970.4	2.04109e+06	116,570	2.13347e+06
Beam-13(Rectangular tube - configured 3 X 2 X 0.25(1)[15])	1	-72,157.8	24,063.5	-740,257	40,871.7	836,478
	2	-77,679	18,477.5	-756,819	51,004	852,975
Beam-14(Angle iron -	1	20,335.6	562,484	2.84275e+06	-91,563.3	3.42557e+06

Beam Name	Joints	Axial(N/m ²)	Bending Dir1(N/m ²)	Bending Dir2(N/m ²)	Torsional (N/m ²)	Upper bound axial and bending(N/m ²)
configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[4]	2	-244,821	550,822	3.6904e+06	47,039.7	4.48604e+06
Beam-15(Square tube - configured 20 X 20 X 2(1)[1])	1	-280.825	1.73665e+06	-398,622	253,886	2.13555e+06
	2	-281.051	-1.45456e+06	399,297	-253,886	1.85414e+06
Beam-16(Trim/Extend18[1])	1	-574,590	941,619	814,942	-46,416.4	2.33115e+06
	2	-574,590	-461,125	-470,582	46,416.4	1.5063e+06
Beam-17(Trim/Extend20[1])	1	-722,077	2.58655e+06	-493,441	-46,692.3	3.80207e+06
	2	-722,077	-1.38905e+06	168,956	46,692.3	2.28008e+06
Beam-18(Square tube - configured 20 X 20 X 2(1)[2])	1	-9,563.53	3.46716e+06	-559,476	144,268	4.03619e+06
	2	-9,564.01	-3.34231e+06	556,901	-144,268	3.90877e+06
Beam-19(Trim/Extend13[2])	1	0	0	0	0	0
	2	184,903	293,539	-1.41827e+06	-18,135.2	1.89671e+06
Beam-20(Trim/Extend11[2])	1	0	0	0	0	0
	2	291,614	-150,186	864,662	-120,976	1.30646e+06
Beam-21(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[3])	1	691,486	909,676	3.03053e+06	-217,225	4.63169e+06
	2	593,964	952,859	2.33666e+06	1,546.16	3.88348e+06
	3	691,486	909,676	3.03053e+06	-217,225	4.63169e+06
Beam-22(Rectangular tube - configured 3 X 2 X 0.25(1)[17])	1	298,071	-222,859	-1.1741e+06	85,934.2	1.69503e+06
	2	339,857	-115,145	-1.05461e+06	-15,858.7	1.50961e+06
Beam-23(Square tube - configured 20 X 20 X 2(1)[3])	1	-47,304.2	3.55036e+06	-585,065	-203,931	4.18273e+06
	2	-47,304.7	-3.58004e+06	586,795	203,931	4.21414e+06
Beam-24(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[1])	1	483,292	1.03984e+06	2.42183e+06	-1,066.03	3.94496e+06
	2	451,800	1.00492e+06	2.40147e+06	5,796.35	3.85819e+06
Beam-25(Trim/Extend20[2])	1	0	0	0	0	0
	2	0	0	0	0	0
Beam-26(Trim/Extend18[2])	1	0	0	0	0	0
	2	0	0	0	0	0
	3	-1.23584	-0.0511579	-1.60188	-0.00531665	2.88887
Beam-27(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[3])	1	177,875	1.03236e+06	1.94903e+06	-362,916	3.15927e+06
	2	119,695	1.45687e+06	2.90044e+06	-258,615	4.477e+06
Beam-28(Trim/Extend22[2])	1	-172,164	42,398.9	1.14101e+06	-54,706.8	1.35557e+06
	2	0	0	0	0	0
	3	-0.93006	-0.0401457	-1.21732	-0.00416954	2.18752
Beam-29(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(1)[1])	1	-31,239.8	702,122	4.13679e+06	208,137	4.87015e+06
	2	-10,295	631,166	4.08237e+06	173,709	4.72383e+06
Beam-30(Angle iron - configured 25 X 25 X 4(2)[2])	1	257,212	863,648	1.76159e+06	84,841.2	2.88245e+06
	2	203,586	825,254	1.60222e+06	19,050.3	2.63106e+06

Table 4: Beam Stresses

Fig 1: Study Results for the stresses, strain and displacement of the bench frame

A. Design of Pipe

The design of a pipe involves the determination of inside diameter of the pipe and its wall thickness as discussed below:
 Inside diameter of the pipe: The inside diameter of the pipe depends upon the quantity of fluid to be delivered, D_i = Inside diameter of the pipe, D_o = outside diameter of the pipe, V = velocity of fluid (meters/min), Q = Quantity of fluid (liters/min), and the quantity of fluid flowing per minute has been recorded.

$$Q = \text{Area} \times \text{velocity} = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \times V \tag{19}$$

Therefore the diameter of the pipe can be calculated.

Also the stress cylinder wall of the pipe can be calculated using Lamé’s formula:

$$\sigma_{t \max} = \frac{p_i (r_o^2 + r_i^2)}{(r_o^2 - r_i^2)} \tag{20}$$

where;

$\sigma_{t \max}$ = maximum tangential stress (MPa)

p_i = internal pressure in the pipe (kPa)

r_i = internal radius of pipe

r_o = external radius of pipe

The thickness of the pipe may be calculated using Lamé’s equation in order to sustain the internal fluid pressure;

$$t = R \left[\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_t + p}{\sigma_t - p}} - 1 \right] \tag{21}$$

Where;

T = thickness of the pipe

R = Inner radius of the pipe,

P = Intensity of internal pressure

σ_t = tangential stress

The pipe’s strength may be calculated using the standard ASTM D1785 table, table 3.6 in Appendix A, which shows that the σ_t for 1" PCV pipe is 5811lb.

Converting 5811lb to Mega pascal (MPa);

$$5811 \text{ lb} = 263.77$$

Therefore,

$$\sigma_t \text{ (MPa)} = \frac{F}{A} \quad (22)$$

$$\sigma_t = \frac{263.17 \times 9.81}{\frac{\pi \times 0.0254^2}{4}} = 5.1 \text{ MPa}$$

A safety factor of 2.5 is used, Therefore, Allowable tensile strength;

$$\sigma_{ta} = \frac{5.1 \times 10^6}{2.5} = 2.04 \text{ MPa}$$

B. Design of Pump

The pump is a single-stage centrifugal pump with a one-horsepower motor. The impeller is developed using the design flow rate, pump head, and pump specific speed as the foundation. As a result, design data are necessary to create a centrifugal pump. The design parameters are as follows while calculating the design.

Flow rate, $Q_{\max} = 35 \text{ l/min}$

Head, $H_{\max} = 35 \text{ m}$

Speed, $n = 2850 \text{ rpm}$

Gravitational acceleration, $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$

Density of water, $\rho = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Specific speed is used to categorize impellers based on their performance and proportions, independent of their actual size or operating speed.

$$\text{Specific Speed: } n_s = 3.65 n \frac{\sqrt{Q}}{H^{1/4}} \quad (23)$$

A pump's capacity, also known as volume flow rate, is the amount of water pushed per unit time. The capacity is proportional to the velocity of the flow in the suction pipe.

$$\text{Capacity: } Q = AV \quad (24)$$

Where A and V are area of pipe and volume flow rate respectively.

C. Water Power and Shaft Power:

Water power is the power transferred to the water by the pump. The flow rate and pump head must be determined in order to compute water power. As a result, in order to deliver a specific level of power to the water, more power must be provided to the pump shaft. This is referred to as brake power. The pump's efficiency dictates how much more power is required at the shaft.

The connection below determines the water power.

$$N = \rho g H Q \quad (25)$$

The shaft power is:

$$\text{Shaft power} = \text{water power} / \eta_o \quad (26)$$

$$\text{Pump efficiency: } \eta_o = \eta_m \times \eta_v \times \eta_r \quad (27)$$

$$\text{Maximum shaft power: } M_{\max} = \alpha_1 \rho g H Q / \eta_o \quad (28)$$

Where; α_1 is the safety factor in charge condition of the work on the pump.

D. Design of the Reservoirs

Fiber glass was used to construct the reservoirs. The material is made up of various composite materials, plastic resin, and glass fiber, as the name suggests. When loaded, plastic resins have a high compressive strength but a low tensile strength, whereas glass fibers have a high tension strength but do not resist compression. GRP becomes a material that resists both compressive and tensile forces well due to the compatibility of each material overcoming the deficiencies of the other. The material was obtained in sheet form, with a thickness of 5mm, and was cut into various measurements and designed to the necessary shaped vessel using

adhesive material for connecting. Water is pumped from the sump tank (large reservoir) and released into the measuring tank as part of the overall design (smaller reservoir).

E. Dimension of the Sump Tank;

Height of the reservoir = 558.8mm
 Length of the reservoir = 469.9mm
 Breath of the reservoir = 457.2mm
 Total volume of reservoir = length × breath × height (29)
 Total volume of reservoir = 558.8mm × 469.9mm × 457.2mm
 Therefore total volume of the circular tank = 120051630.864mm³ = 120.05L

Fig. 2: Finite Element Analysis (FEA) for the Sump Reservoir

Name	Type	Min	Max
Stress1	VON: von Mises Stress	6.358e+02N/m ² Node: 6874	2.293e+07N/m ² Node: 14550
Displacement1	URES: Resultant Displacement	0.000e+00mm Node: 178	3.417e+01mm Node: 19933

<p>Part1-Static 1-Stress-Stress1</p>			
<p>Part1-Static 1-Displacement-Displacement1</p>			

Fig. 3: Study Results for the Static Stress and Displacement of the Reservoir

F. Dimension of the Measuring Tank;

Height of the reservoir = 431.8mm
 Length of the reservoir = 457.2mm
 Width of the reservoir = 431.8mm

Total volume of reservoir = length \times breath \times height (30)

Total volume of reservoir = 457.2mm \times 431.8mm \times 431.8mm

Therefore total volume of the circular tank = 85245506.928mm³ = 85.25L

VI. THE MANUFACTURING METHODOLOGY

A. *Machining*: This refers to any of the different procedures for cutting raw material into a specified form and size using a controlled material-removal process. Cutting, drilling and grinding are the machining procedures employed in this design.

- **Cutting operation;**
- **Drilling operation;** this is a cost-effective method of removing a considerable amount of metal in order to create a semi-precision round hole or cavity. This is done in order to drill holes for fasteners.
- **Grinding operation;** this is a cutting operation that involves the use of abrasive particles. By eliminating any leftover undesired components from the surface, the grinding operation improves the surface polish and tightens the tolerance. Grinding machines are used to manufacture items that are the same form, size, and finish.

B. *Joining*: The following is a list of the methods that were utilized in the joining operation:

- **Welding;** the hollow mild steel square pipe is heated and melted using gas welding and arc welding in some areas in this procedure, resulting in the linked portions functioning as one. It's utilized to produce the frame.
- **Adhesive;** Polymers are the most well-known adhesives, allowing various materials to be joined at temperatures below 200°C. Adhesive bonding (also known as gluing or glue bonding) is a wafer bonding technique that involves the use of an intermediary layer to link substrates of various materials. It is used to connect pipes and fittings in this case, and the kind used is araldite. Araldite is a high-performance adhesive that bonds ceramics, wood, chipboard, glass, metal, and most hard

plastics. Free of solvents, heat and cold resistant, as well as water and oil resistant. Three essential characteristics must be met in order to generate a good surface for adhesive bonding of plastics: To develop a strong boundary layer, the provided material's weak boundary layer must be eliminated or chemically changed.

- **Degreasing;** the adhered is to be wiped with solvent or an aqueous detergent solution to clean the surface of any oils following degreasing process. After degreasing, a good test to determine cleanliness of the surface is to use a drop of water. If the drop spreads on the surface, a low contact angle and good wettability has been achieved, which indicates the surface is clean and ready for application of the adhesive. If the drop beads up or retains its shape, the degreasing process should be repeated.
- **Abrasion;** to roughen the surface and remove any loose material, the adherent is sanded or grit blasted using an abrasive substance. In comparison to a relatively smooth surface, rough surfaces make stronger connections because they have a larger surface area for the adhesive to attach to. After abrasion, the adherent should be cleaned with solvent or an aqueous detergent solution to remove any oils or loose particles, and then dried. The glue is then applied when this process is completed.
- **Coating;** this is a coating that is applied to an object's surface, also known as the substrate. The coating can be applied for ornamental, utilitarian, or both purposes. The coating may be an all-over coating that covers the entire substrate or a partial coating that just covers sections of the substrate. Car paint was employed in the coating process of this device, which has the dual purpose of preserving the substrate while also being beautiful.

Plate 1: Cutting operations

Plate 2: Joining Operations

Plate 3: Grinding and Smoothing Operations

C. Fabrication Methodology

Various methods were examined in the development of the centrifugal pump test rig, including:

- **Research:** This step entails carefully considering information sourcing, data gathering, and data assessment from the internet or other sources in order to gain the knowledge needed to build the centrifugal pump test rig.
- **Data compilation:** In this step, the acquired data from the study is integrated and examined in order to arrive at a certain operation sequence. The designer can follow the data compilation process to design the equipment step by step.
- **Material selection:** This process involves the cost of materials used for the manufacturing process, with the goal of lowering production costs while improving the quality and dependability of the chosen material.
- **Design:** Following the material selection, the pieces chosen are considered and their dimensions are computed.

- **Fabrication:** Work is done on the many pieces that make up the system at this step to get them to the shape and size necessary for the design. Various manufacturing procedures are carried out in this process.
- **Assembly;** this entails bringing all of the various sections or parts that have been worked on together to make the system. The reservoirs were attached to the frame after the frame was completed. We installed the electrical pump and connected the pipes to it; the horizontal pipe from the pump's suction side was linked to the reservoir, while the vertical pipe from the pump's discharge side was connected to the reservoir. As the discharge line links to the receiving reservoir, the water flow meter was also attached.

Finally, powering the whole unit and testing.

Plate 4:A pictorial view of the finished Centrifugal pump test bed

VII. METHODS

A. Procedure

Make sure the advanced inverter is turned on and the pump is adjusted to 50% before starting the motor. The pump speed will be increased by the interface until it reaches the desired value. Start the motor by closing the ball valve on the discharge line. Check to see whether the discharge pressure of the pump rises. If the pump does not release pressure after ten seconds, it is most likely dry and has to be primed. Close the flow meter cap and start the pump again to prime the pump, or partly close and open the

inlet valves a few times to help prime the system and remove any bubbles stuck inside the valve mechanism. Make sure the intake valve is completely open.

To give a flow rate of $Q = 0$, close the ball valve. (Be aware that if the ball valve is closed or almost closed, the back pressure created is outside of normal operating norms, and the pump may not work smoothly.) As the trial goes, the pump should begin to run more smoothly.) Allow the pump to run for a few minutes before collecting data; during this

time, open and close the discharge valve as needed and monitor the suction and discharge pressure gauges.

Allow the readings of the water flow meter and the pressure gauges to stabilize and record the values at each increment by opening the gates valve (discharge valve) in modest increments.

Tabulate a list of your findings. When the discharge valve (head valve) was closed, the load on the pump increased and the motor speed fell; however, when the discharge valve was opened, the load on the pump decreased and the motor speed rose.

Repeat the operation with the advanced inverter Variable Frequency Drive (VFD) at 60 percent, 80 percent, 90 percent, and 100 percent of the manufacturer's specified pump speed. Tabulate your data of suction pressure,

discharge pressure, flow rate, pipe diameter, input power, torque at each speed, and efficiency each time.

Switch off the pump, and if you're not going to do another workout right away, turn off the complete system and drain the water from the reservoir.

B. Bill of Engineering Measurement and Evaluation

One of the most essential elements that were carefully examined during the design of the centrifugal pump test bed was material selection. The cost of the materials required for the centrifugal pump test bed's design and construction. The materials' availability on the market, as well as their appropriateness for the design, were taken into account. Transportation, typing or photocopying, communication, and incidental costs might all be ascribed to other expenses. The materials obtained, as well as their cost and purchased amount, were recorded in the table below;

S/N	Part	Quantity	Cost (#)
1	Flow control valve	2	6,000
2	Water Flow meter	1	4,500
3	Advanced inverter	1	9,000
4	Stop watch	1	500
5	Valves	5	5,000
6	Pressure gauges	2	6,000
7	Centrifugal Pump (0.5hp)	1	9,000
8	Fittings	5	27,240
9	Adhesive	2	5,400
10	Bench Frame	1	17,000
11	Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) Pipes	6	1,500
12	Polyethylene Circular tank	1	25,500
13	Caster wheels	4	4,000
14	Strainers	2	1000
		Total	121,640

Table 5: Bill of Engineering Measurement and Evaluation (BEME)

VIII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results and Calculation

On a copy of the single pump test sheet or in the table below, note the results.

Calculate the volume flow rate from the volumetric measuring tank if one was utilized, from

$$: \dot{Q} = Q/t \tag{31}$$

Calculate the manometric head from

$$: H = \frac{(P_2 - P_1)}{\rho g} \tag{32}$$

The hydraulic power can be calculated from:

$$W_{out} = \rho g H \dot{Q} \tag{33}$$

$$h = \frac{W_{out}}{W_{in}} \tag{34}$$

Calculate the overall efficiency from:

For the data of the constant speed and constant voltage tests, plot the pump characteristics as a single graph of manometric head against volumetric flow rate.

For each set of findings, plot graphs of hydraulic power and total efficiency against flow rate. This graph may be used for interpolation to generate values that can be used to construct contours of constant hydraulic power and constant efficiency onto the pump characteristics if needed.

Before plotting the numerous graphs required to characterize a centrifugal pump, make sure to enter your calculations and findings in the tables on the following page.

Pump inlet Suction Pressure [Bar]	Pump outlet Delivery Pressure [Bar]	Total Head H [m]	Pump Speed N [RPM]	Pump Torque T[Nm]	Hydraulic Power W_{out} [W]	Flow rate Q[m ³ /s]	Total Power Input [W]	Efficiency [%]
-0.00196133	0.583155	5.97	2850	0.302	0	0	90	0
-0.00196133	0.343233	3.52	2850	0.369	4.627	0.000134	110	0.042
-0.00196133	0.2647796	2.72	2850	0.395	5.550	0.000208	118	0.047
-0.00196133	0.1569064	1.619	2850	0.476	5.674	0.000357	142	0.039
-0.00196133	0.0392266	0.419	2850	0.519	1.9196	0.000467	155	0.012

Table 6.0: Characteristic reading of the pump taken at Constant Pump speed: 2850 rpm

B. RESULTS

The performance test results are plotted in a graphical fashion, with power input vs flow rate (W_{in} vs Q) for pump speed: 2850 rpm on one graph, head versus flow rate (H_p vs Q) for same pump speed on another graph, and efficiency

versus flow rate (η_p vs Q) for same pump speed on a final graph. The experimental H_p vs Q , W_{in} vs Q and η_p vs Q graphs are described, and comments on the influence of pump speed are offered.

Fig 4: A graph showing power input against flow rate, with the centrifugal pump's characteristic curve measured simultaneously at 2850 rpm. The flow rate and shaft power are depicted in relative units.

Fig. 5: At constant speed of 2850 rpm, a graph of head vs flow rate is used to determine the centrifugal pump's characteristic curve. The flow rate and shaft power are shown with relative units.

Fig 6.0: Resulting graph of Efficiency against flow rate estimates for a centrifugal pump driven by a 0.5Hp motor and frequency converter at constant pump speed of 2850rpm.

C. DISCUSSION

The H-Q and h_o -Q curves are used to form the braking power (BP) or shaft power (SP) vs flow rate (Q) curve for a pump. The BP-Q curve's shape is determined by the pump's particular speed and impeller design. Figure 4.0 illustrates that for radial flow impellers, BP rises to a peak and then falls somewhat as Q rises from zero. BP grows progressively from a nonzero value as Q increases for mixed flow impellers. Axial flow impellers, on the other hand, have a maximum BP when Q is 0 and gradually drop as Q grows. To reduce the start-up load on axial flow pumps, the discharge-side valve (or discharge valve) should be open to the atmosphere when they are turned on. When radial flow and mixed flow pumps are started, the discharge-side valve should be closed.

The head-discharge curve (H-Q curve) is a graph that shows how a pump's head corresponds to the amount of water pushed per unit time (i.e., discharge of the pump). In general, as a pump's discharge increases, the head generated by the pump gradually decreases (Fig. 5.0). The design head or normal head, and the design discharge or normal discharge of a pump are the head and discharge values that correspond to the greatest efficiency.

The H-Q curve changes form depending on the speed. As discharge (Q) grows from zero, the head of radial flow impellers reduces just little before rapidly dropping. Mixed and axial flow impellers have less severe H-Q curve slope shifts than radial flow impellers. In circumstances where head must stay practically constant while Q fluctuates, radial flow impellers working on the flat region of their H-Q curves function effectively (e.g., as in set-move systems where the number of operating laterals varies during the irrigation season). When a reasonably constant Q is sought but H is predicted to fluctuate (e.g., water sources such as a well, small stream, or small reservoir), impellers with greater specific speeds will likely work the best.

Fig. 6.0 shows the pump efficiency against discharge (h_o -Q) curves for common centrifugal pumps. As Q rises from zero, the overall efficiency (h_o) of a pump steadily

grows to a peak, then drops as Q rises higher. For a particular type of impeller, there is usually just one peak efficiency.

Specific speed, impeller design, and pump discharge all affect potential pump efficiency. The greater capacity pumps should have the maximum efficiency, according to this figure. The types of materials used in construction, the finish on castings, the quality of machining, and the type and quality of bearings used all affect overall efficiency (h_o). Impellers with extraordinarily smooth surfaces, for example, are more efficient than impellers with rougher surfaces.

IX. CONCLUSION

The design and building of a centrifugal pump test bed are the focus of this project. Mild steel square hollow pipes, PVC valve gauge taps, PVC pipes, a flow meter, and a cast iron centrifugal surface pump were used to build the centrifugal pump test bed. The goal of this study was to find the best material for a laboratory fluid flow apparatus that allows for the measurement of flow in pipes and the deduction of various pump curve features at varied constant speeds with the same diameter impeller blade. The materials were sourced locally, and the building was completed at the university workshop. The centrifugal-pump, as previously said, is a hydraulic machine that uses centrifugal force to transform mechanical energy into hydraulic energy. The centrifugal pump is powered by an electric motor and pulls fluid (water) from a water storage tank before delivering it to a tank via a flow control valve. We were able to use the demonstration unit to do all of the experiments required to completely describe a centrifugal pump at varied constant speeds with the same impeller diameter blade. Because centrifugal pumps are used to transport liquids from one location to another, they are an effective tool for teaching students the relationships between pressure or head, volumetric flow rate, shaft rotational speeds, and input and output powers, effectively bridging the gap between theory and practice. The test bed is designed to give students an instructional tool that they may use to conduct various

experiments to show the physical and functional links between these characteristics.

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